

PREVALENCE AND SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC PREDICTORS OF SELF-MEDICATION AMONG NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Self-medication, defined as the use of medications for self-diagnosed conditions without professional consultation, is a growing public health concern, particularly among university students. This descriptive cross-sectional study assessed the prevalence and determinants of self-medication among 234 undergraduate students using a structured questionnaire and analyzing data with IBM SPSS Statistics (version 26). The study found a high self-medication prevalence of 95.7%, with pain relief and headaches being the most frequently reported reasons (73.9%). The main determinant factor was ease and accessibility of medications (52.6%). Although knowledge levels significantly influenced students' perceptions of self-medication safety, predictors were not analyzed with multivariate methods; thus, independent predictors cannot be conclusively established. These findings underscore the urgent need for targeted interventions, including health education, regulation of medication access, and improved availability of affordable professional healthcare, to reduce reliance on self-medication and promote safer health practices among students.

Keywords: Self-medication, home remedies, public health, undergraduate students, health education

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INTRODUCTION

Self-medication involves the use of medications to treat self-diagnosed illnesses or symptoms, or the sporadic or continuous use of prescription medications for recurrent or chronic conditions without consultation with a healthcare professional (WHO, 2020). This practice often includes over-the-counter (OTC) medications, which are generally considered safe when used appropriately. However, individual perceptions of illness, shaped by personal beliefs and prior experiences, strongly influence health-seeking behaviors and treatment choices (Orji and Moffatt, 2018). While some individuals rely on home remedies or allow symptoms to resolve naturally, others seek professional advice or utilize OTC medications (Lin *et al.*, 2022).

Globally, self-medication is widespread, recognized as a component of healthcare practices in both developed and developing countries (Jankowska-Piekarska and

Rosińska, 2020; Ayalew, 2017; Himmel and Kussmann, 2023). Its rising prevalence is attributed to factors such as changing lifestyles, socioeconomic conditions, ease of access to medications, increased capacity for self-care, and broader availability of pharmaceuticals (Almasdy and Sharrif, 2011). In resource-limited settings, including Nigeria, self-medication addresses a substantial proportion of healthcare needs due to its perceived cost-effectiveness, with estimates suggesting that 60–80% of health concerns are managed in this way (Abate *et al.*, 2025; Khan, 2011; Mossa, 2012).

University students represent a population particularly prone to self-medication, commonly using OTC drugs for ailments such as headaches, fever, and minor infections (Al-Kubaisi *et al.*, 2022). While self-medication can provide convenience and rapid symptom relief, it carries risks, including medication

misuse, antibiotic resistance, masking of serious conditions, and adverse drug reactions (WHO, 2022). Factors influencing self-medication among students include financial constraints, prior experiences with similar health issues, limited time to consult healthcare providers, and easy access to medications (Ahmed and Khan, 2021). Additionally, patterns of self-medication can vary across demographic factors such as gender, age, academic discipline, and socioeconomic status, highlighting the complexity of this public health issue.

Studies in developing countries indicate that knowledge gaps about medication risks and cultural tendencies toward self-care contribute to high rates of self-medication among university students (Banerjee *et al.*, 2021). In Nigeria, healthcare infrastructure deficits and perceptions of high cost or limited access may exacerbate this practice (Olayemi *et al.*, 2020). Understanding the socio-demographic factors influencing self-medication is therefore critical for designing interventions that promote safe medication use and appropriate healthcare-seeking behaviors.

Given these considerations, this study aimed to assess the prevalence and determinants of self-medication among undergraduate students, with attention to demographic variables such as age, gender, and socioeconomic background. The findings are intended to inform evidence-based public health strategies to mitigate the risks associated with self-medication and support safer health practices within student populations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting: This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional design to investigate self-medication practices among undergraduate students at Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria. Data were collected using structured self-administered questionnaires.

Study Population and Sample Size: The study population comprised undergraduate students aged 18–25 years enrolled at Ambrose Alli University. A total of 234 students, drawn from various faculties, academic disciplines, and levels of study, participated in the study. Both male and female students were represented, covering a range of socioeconomic backgrounds. The sample size was calculated using a standard formula, assuming a 95% confidence level

and a 5% margin of error, ensuring statistical reliability and generalizability to the broader student population.

Sampling Methods: A stratified sampling approach was applied to ensure adequate representation across key sociodemographic variables, including gender, academic discipline, and year of study. Within each stratum, systematic random sampling was conducted by selecting students from predefined lists. This method minimized bias while maintaining randomization.

1. **Data Collection Method:** Data were collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire comprising open- and closed-ended questions. The instrument included the following sections:
2. **Demographic Data:** Age, gender, academic faculty/discipline, residence (on/off campus), and year of study.
3. **Self-Medication Practices:** Frequency of self-medication, common health conditions treated, types of medications used, and primary sources of medications.
4. **Knowledge and Awareness:** Participants' awareness of medication risks and accessibility of professional medical care.

Socioeconomic and Influencing Factors: Perceived impact of financial constraints, peer influence, and family practices on self-medication decisions.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval was obtained from the Ambrose Alli University Ethics Committee (approval number [004/25]). All participants provided informed consent prior to completing the questionnaire, ensuring voluntary participation and understanding of the study's objectives.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26.0. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize demographic characteristics, knowledge levels, and self-medication practices. Associations between categorical variables were assessed using Chi-square

tests of independence, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Limitation Regarding Predictors: While the study aimed to explore factors associated with self-medication, the cross-sectional design and sample size did not permit multivariate analysis, such as logistic regression, to robustly identify independent predictors. Consequently, the study reports associations descriptively and recognizes that causal or independent predictive relationships cannot be inferred from the data. This limitation is acknowledged explicitly in the discussion and interpretation of findings

RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics

The study included 234 undergraduate students aged 18–25 years. The largest age group, 116 participants (49.6%), was between 22 and 25 years. Female students constituted 138 (59.0%) of the sample. Most participants, 177 (75.6%), were in their 400 or 500 level of study. Health Sciences was the predominant field of study, accounting for 180 students (76.9%). Majority of participants resided off-campus ($n=204$; 87.2%). These demographics reflect a predominantly young, female, and health-focused student population.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Variables	Categories	Frequency (n=234)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	<18	3	1.3
	18–21	73	31.2
	22–25	116	49.6
	≥ 26	42	17.9
Gender	Male	96	41.0
	Female	138	59.0
Level of Study	100	6	2.7
	200	20	8.5
	300	31	13.2
	400/500	177	75.6
Field of Study	Health Sciences	180	76.9
	Engineering	18	7.7
	Arts & Humanities	20	8.5
	Management Sciences	16	6.8
Residence	On Campus	3	1.3
	Off Campus	204	87.2
	With Family	9	3.8
	Other	18	7.7

Knowledge and Awareness of Self-Medication

Significant associations were observed between students’ knowledge levels and their beliefs regarding the safety of self-medication (p = 0.034). Knowledge levels were unevenly distributed, with certain categories significantly more prevalent (Chi-square =

125.19, p < 0.001). Barriers to healthcare access, particularly cost and income limitations, were reported by most participants (Chi-square = 128.62, p < 0.001). No significant association was observed between health insurance ownership and perceived accessibility to healthcare (p = 0.116).

Table 2: Knowledge and Healthcare Access

Variable/Question	Test Type	Chi-Square	p-value	Interpretation
Knowledge Levels	Goodness of Fit	125.19	<0.001*	Certain knowledge categories are significantly more prevalent
Barriers to Healthcare Access	Goodness of Fit	128.62	<0.001*	Cost/income barriers are most reported
Knowledge vs. Belief in Self-Medication	Test of Independence	11.37	0.034	Knowledge level significantly influences beliefs on self-medication safety
Health Insurance vs. Healthcare Accessibility	Test of Independence	7.41	0.116	No significant association

*Significance indicated at $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 3: Self-Medication Practices

Variables/Questions	Categories	Frequency (n=234)	Percentage (%)
Ever practiced self-medication	Yes	224	95.7
	No	10	4.3
Frequency of self-medication	Regular/Frequent	26	11.1
	Occasionally	114	48.7
	Continuously	3	1.3
	Rarely	91	38.9
Common health conditions	Pain/Headaches	173	73.9
	Cold/Flu	33	14.1
	Digestive issues	6	2.6
	Menstrual pain	22	9.4
Source of medications	Local pharmacies	135	57.7
	Friends/Family	40	17.1
	OTC	35	15.0
	Leftover prescription	24	10.3
Consultation with healthcare professionals	Rarely	100	42.7
	Occasionally	95	40.6
	Regular/Frequent	39	16.7
	Continuously	0	0

Self-Medication Practices

Self-medication was highly prevalent, reported by 224 participants (95.7%). Occasional use was the most common frequency (48.7%), followed by rare use (38.9%). Pain relief and headaches were the most frequent reasons for self-medication (73.9%), with local pharmacies serving as the primary source of medications (57.7%). Consultation with healthcare professionals was infrequent; 42.7% reported rarely seeking professional advice despite 44.9% receiving guidance from healthcare professionals.

Determinant Factors for Self-Medication

The primary determinants were ease of access (52.6%) and cost/income constraints (36.8%). Guidance for self-medication was mainly sourced from healthcare professionals (44.9%) and personal networks (34.6%). Stress levels were reported as high by 42.3% of students, and 70.5% reported feeling strongly supported by friends and family.

Table 4: Determinant Factors

Variables/Questions	Categories	Frequency (n=234)	Percentage (%)
Decision influencers	Ease/Accessibility	123	52.6
	Cost/Income	86	36.8
	Environment/Location	23	9.8
	Stigmatization	2	0.8
Sources of self-medication guidance	Healthcare professionals	105	44.9
	Friends/Family	81	34.6
	Online information	43	18.4
	Media	5	2.1
Stress levels	Very stressed	99	42.3
	Not very stressed	80	34.2
	Somewhat stressed	47	15.8
	Not at all	18	7.7
Perceived support	Very supported	165	70.5
	Not very supported	42	17.9
	Somewhat supported	23	9.8
	Not at all	4	1.8

Limitation on Predictive Analysis

It is recognized that, due to the study's design and sample size, independent predictors of self-medication could not be formally determined through multivariate analysis. Associations are reported descriptively, and causal inferences cannot be drawn. This limitation is explicitly acknowledged in the interpretation of findings.

DISCUSSION

This study found a very high prevalence of self-medication (95.7%) among undergraduate students at Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma. This indicates that self-medication is a deeply embedded health-seeking behavior within this student population. Most students reported occasional use, and the practice was primarily for pain relief and headaches. Local pharmacies were the most common source of medications, while cost and ease of access were the dominant determinants influencing self-medication behavior. These findings collectively point to a pattern of convenience-driven and economically motivated self-care practices among Nigerian university students.

The observed prevalence is consistent with earlier studies conducted among student populations in similar contexts. Osemene and Lamikanra (2012) reported 91.4% prevalence among university students in southwestern Nigeria, while Suciú et al. (2024) and Araia et al. (2019) documented prevalence rates of 96% and 79.2%, respectively, in other developing settings. The current study's higher prevalence may be partly due to the predominance of Health Sciences students in the sample, as these individuals may perceive themselves as more knowledgeable about medications and therefore more confident in self-prescribing. However, this overconfidence may also mask inadequate understanding of drug risks and proper dosage.

The study further showed that most students engaged in self-medication for non-severe health conditions such as headaches, common colds, and menstrual pain—conditions perceived as minor and manageable without professional consultation. This is consistent with Ahmed and Khan (2021) and Moraes and Costa (2022), who found that students in resource-limited contexts tend to self-medicate for common ailments rather than chronic or severe illnesses. The reliance on

local pharmacies as primary medication sources underscores the critical role of these outlets in determining self-medication patterns. Pharmacies often serve as the first point of care in many Nigerian communities, which, while convenient, also facilitates unsupervised access to drugs.

Demographically, the predominance of Health Sciences students (76.9%) may have influenced the overall level of awareness and confidence in using medications without prescriptions. Although knowledge levels were generally high, the study found a statistically significant relationship between knowledge and belief in the safety of self-medication ($p = 0.034$), suggesting that even well-informed students may underestimate potential risks. This highlights the complexity of the knowledge-behavior gap: understanding drug use principles does not necessarily translate to safe practice.

Contrary to expectations, gender and level of study were not strong differentiators of self-medication behavior. The marginally higher prevalence among female students may reflect their greater engagement in health-related self-care, particularly for menstrual pain and stress-related conditions. This aligns with findings by Banerjee et al. (2021), who reported that gender differences in self-medication practices are often context-dependent and influenced by cultural norms regarding health-seeking behavior.

Financial and accessibility constraints were the most influential factors driving self-medication in this study. These findings support earlier assertions that in low- and middle-income countries, limited access to affordable healthcare pushes individuals toward self-care alternatives (Olayemi et al., 2020; Abate et al., 2025). The significance of cost barriers further reflects structural deficiencies in student healthcare systems, where consultation fees, long waiting times, and inadequate health insurance coverage discourage formal care.

Overall, the study's findings reinforce the notion that self-medication among university students is shaped by a combination of economic, behavioral, and systemic factors. High prevalence, easy access to medications, and insufficient regulatory oversight contribute to the persistence of the practice. Although knowledge of

medications is relatively high, misconceptions about safety and the perceived triviality of minor ailments perpetuate risky self-medication behaviors.

LIMITATIONS

While this study identified important associations between self-medication practices and influencing factors, it did not determine independent predictors due to its descriptive cross-sectional design and limited sample size. Multivariate analysis, such as logistic regression, could not be conducted; therefore, causal relationships or predictive strengths of the identified factors were not established. Additionally, the reliance on self-reported data introduces potential recall and social desirability biases, and the predominance of Health Sciences students may limit the generalizability of findings to the broader university population. Future studies employing larger, multi-institutional samples and more advanced analytical methods are recommended to address these gaps.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated a very high prevalence of self-medication among undergraduate students at Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, indicating that the practice is both common and culturally accepted within this academic community. The majority of respondents reported occasional use of medications without professional consultation, primarily for minor conditions such as headaches, fever, and menstrual pain. Local pharmacies and prior experiences were the main sources of medication and guidance, emphasizing accessibility and perceived familiarity as key drivers.

Cost and ease of access were identified as the most influential determinants of self-medication, reflecting broader structural and economic challenges faced by students in accessing formal healthcare services. Although the predominance of Health Sciences students likely contributed to higher levels of drug-related knowledge, this did not necessarily translate into safer practices, suggesting a gap between awareness and responsible medication use.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Universities should strengthen health education campaigns emphasizing the safe use

of medications, potential risks of drug misuse, and appropriate times to seek professional care.

2. Institutions should improve student access to on-campus or subsidized healthcare services to reduce financial and logistical barriers that encourage self-medication.
3. Local pharmacies should be encouraged to enforce stricter guidelines on OTC drug sales and promote responsible dispensing practices through awareness partnerships with universities.
4. Health-related faculties should incorporate modules on rational drug use and public health implications of self-medication to build responsible health behaviors among future professionals.
5. Further multi-center studies using multivariate statistical methods are needed to identify robust predictors of self-medication and evaluate the effectiveness of targeted interventions over time.

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AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

Oluwabunmi C. O. for data collection; Vidona W.B for research design; Ehebha S.E. for conceptualization, Monday A.B. for survey design; Elijah S.O. for data review; Obiolor A. for manuscript first editing; Lawson C. for manuscript second editing; Ijeoma P.A. for manuscript third editing; Nwanama E.K. for first manuscript draft; Ekwueme P.E for second manuscript draft.

